

Comments on Wikimedia demographic studies

Information about this document

Abstract: Recently two studies on Wikimedia editors were performed. One was global distributing online questionnaires to probability strata selected participants of various Wikimedia projects in different parts of the world, and the other one was a content analysis of personal pages of active contributors on Czech Wikipedia. Results show, that most of the contributors are males with tertiary education, living in cities. The Czech community seems to get older, but content analysis does not look like to be the best way to research the editor demographic. Rather data analysis with the consequent inquiries on various language mutations is recommended. But at first work on the classification of editors by their activity would be necessary.

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Introduction

In the following lines, I will briefly evaluate two studies that recently investigated sociodemographic characteristics of volunteers contributing to Wikimedia projects (wiki projects for short). Wikimedia projects is a collective designation of twelve projects focused on the creation of electronic documents available under free licenses, open education, open science, and open collaboration in the development of open software. The whole family of projects, which are further divided by individual languages, is maintained by the San Francisco-based Wikimedia Foundation.

Evaluated research studies

The researches that I will evaluate are Community Insights 2023¹ and Editors of the Czech Wikipedia.² The first study evaluated the editors of all wiki projects, and the second focused only on the editors of the Czech Wikipedia. Who conducts the Community Insights research is not clear from the project's pages on the Wikimedia community portal, but it is likely to be the Wikimedia Foundation itself, or a specialized organization hired for this purpose. The authors of the Czech study are students of the Faculty of Arts in the fields of sociology and information science.

Methodology and its evaluation

In the first case, a questionnaire online survey was used. The researchers carried out a stratified probability selection in which they divided the respondents into strata according to individual wiki projects or groups of projects and further selected them according to their activity on Wikimedia projects, and the possibility to contact respondents by e-mail. They considered active editors who made 10 edits in the 3 months prior to the study. The return rate was 12.1 %, i.e. 2870 completed questionnaires.

Subsequently, in order to reduce the number of responses between groups, weighting was carried out using the "inverse propensity score matching by project strata and edit bin". Most of the analyzes were subjected to Pearson's chi-squared test with "z-test comparisons between categories to understand where differences were evident".

The return rate of 12.1 % is a relatively small number for research on the Internet, and even if the return rate also decreases for other surveys in time, it ranges between 20–30 % in the Czech Republic. It is therefore a question of whether the selection methodology does not have a negative effect on the return, especially addressing editors who, from my point of view, have sporadic activity (5 edits a month). The second reason may be the cultural diversity of the respondents or their possibilities at the time of the research.

Another problem I would see is that although the report states that a probabilistic selection was made, by excluding editors without email, it changed to non-probable. Why would editors who do not list a contact not be appropriate study participants? After all, the researcher could contact them on discussion pages, which is the usual way of communication. I am not sure that a public call to such an extent would in any way influence the ways of filling out questionnaires. Possibly this was done to protect editors of the smaller projects from kind of discrimination?

1 Wikimedia Contributors. Community Insights 2023. Available online: https://meta.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?title=Community_Insights/Community_Insights_2023_Report&oldid=25360055

2 Adéla Fejková, Kristina Komissarová, Jan Lochman. 2022. *Editori české Wikipedie*. (unpublished)

Czech research was conducted in the form of anonymized content analysis. We worked with the personal and discussion pages of editors who had made more than 100 edits in the month before the research and had some information on their personal page. Out of a total of 559,521 registered accounts, we reached 99. When obtaining information, this information was coded and then a statistical analysis was carried out in the form of a sum, calculation of percentages, and median.

When evaluating the reliability of the data and the fact that the researcher only has at his disposal what someone leaves about himself, I would not consider this type of exploratory research to be the most suitable in this case. I would lean towards a combination of data analysis and a subsequent questionnaire survey. Problems that can affect the content analysis, in this case, are information that becomes outdated over time and that no one updates. It is not known how carefully the editors of the Czech Wikipedia update their personal information. A certain solution here would look at the historical revisions of their pages, whether they were changing the information in time and what were their previous artifacts on the researched pages.

Another problem I would see in the methodology is that editors without personal page were eliminated. With no personal page, one can still conduct a content analysis on their discussion page.

Results and comparisons

Although both studies worked with different active editors, they agree on the issue of gender. The majority of the world and Czech population is made up of males, and only around 10 % are females. Information on gender on Czech Wikipedia was taken from the use of grammatical gender. That would not cover people who identify themselves with other genders than male/female, global inquiry had such other choices.

In terms of age, the global study points out that the majority of editors are young people placed in two age groups ranging from 18 to 34 years old. In the Czech study, the median was 44 +/- 1 years. That would point out, that most Czech editors are way older than global counts, but here I should point out that information providing age was in small numbers and thus the results may not be reliable.

In addition, I have extracted dates of creation of accounts of users researched in the Czech study. This provides us with the so-called wiki age, which is the age of the user since his registration. The youngest editors at that time were a few months old, the oldest 16 years old. For older editors, this does not mean that they edit for the whole of their wiki life, but just that they have account for that time. Someone can register, edit for a while, then take a break for a few years or months and then continue again.

Determining the wikiage can help with determining which age group is less present. From previous, but also this Global study we can read, that younger editors, i.e. younger than 18 or 16 years old are rare. This is explained by the fact, that the structure of Wikipedia articles is advanced, and for its creation, a user needs more advanced skills, gained usually in tertiary education. So if the counted median for the sample group was 11 years of wiki age), it indicates that people, who lie around the median will be at least the age 27, 31, or older. Applying media of the wiki age, to the youngest group possible (ages 16 and 20) takes us to the conclusion, that the group of 18 to 24 might be less frequent on the Czech Wikipedia.

The other two findings were not comparable. The global study focused on minor ethnic groups and education, Czech study on the place of residence and hobbies.

Results for education show, that most editors have a certain type of tertiary education. This is probably linked to the fact explained above, that only university students or graduates have enough skills to master the creation of Wikipedia articles. That's why I would expect similar results for the Czech community.

Finally, not a surprise in the Czech study, that most of the participants are located in big cities or nearby. This may correlate with a prevalent presence of males, by the means that Wikipedia was more techy at the beginning. Participants had to master not only the article creation process but HTML-like tags to format their texts. Thus it was more accessible for people like coders, who already had a similar experience and at that time mostly males, staying in bigger agglomerations and studying at the universities or working for tech companies. What is more surprising today, is that Wikipedia for the last about 10 years a new editor, but the number of women has not risen.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we may say that a study on the activity of the user may be needed. It's not a big deal to set specific criteria and filter users fitting in a specific group of activity. The question is if and how the activity of users represents Wikimedia/pedia population. Whether it's a uniform community or users with certain edit patterns are way different than others.

For sure, also a further investigation focusing on different language Wikipedias or participants of other projects from the Wikimedia family would be useful to have a deeper understanding of each project community. Then we may do a meta-analysis to compare these studies and get a better understanding of the global Wikimedia community or a certain portion of it.